

HYPERTROPHIC SCAR TREATMENT USING A NEW LASER COMBINATION IN SURGICAL PRACTICE.

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ABSTRACT

In dermatology and plastic surgery, scars continue to be one of the most prevalent issues. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), around 100 million people get scars following surgery and trauma each year. Scar tissue can cause substantial cosmetic discomfort, and in some circumstances - and functional limits, especially when located in the area of joints or face. The goal of contemporary scar treatment methods is to restore the skin's structure and functionality in addition to enhancing appearance. For severe and longstanding scars, conventional techniques (ointments, silicone plates, corticosteroid injections) are frequently insufficient [1, 2]. Laser therapy has been acknowledged during the last two decades as an effective and safe way of scar tissue repair

Introduction. In dermatology and plastic surgery, scars continue to be one of the most prevalent issues. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), around 100 million people get scars following surgery and trauma each year. Scar tissue can cause substantial cosmetic discomfort, and in some circumstances - and functional limits, especially when located in the area of joints or face. The goal of contemporary scar treatment methods is to restore the skin's structure and functionality in addition to enhancing appearance. For severe and longstanding scars, conventional techniques (ointments, silicone plates, corticosteroid injections) are frequently insufficient [1, 2]. Laser therapy has been acknowledged during the last two decades as an effective and safe way of scar tissue repair. Fractional CO₂ laser stimulates collagen remodeling and improves skin texture, whereas pulsed red laser (595 nm) lowers vascularization and inflammation, which is crucial for hypertrophic and keloid scars. The combination of these two technologies allows comprehensive therapy of numerous components of the scar process, boosting the effectiveness of treatment and decreasing the rehabilitation period. This approach is validated by several clinical investigations, which supports its relevance and possibilities in modern practice [3,4,5].

Material and Methods. 60 patients, 38 women and 22 men, ranging in age from 20 to 55 (mean age: 36.4 ± 8.2 years), with hypertrophic (n = 35), atrophic (n = 20), and keloid (n =

5) scars, were included in the study. The duration of scarring ranged from 6 months to 5 years. There were no systemic contraindications to laser treatment or acute inflammatory skin conditions in the patients. Patients were treated at RS laser clinic between 2022 and 2025.

Results. The study comprised sixty patients who received treatment with tacrolimus ointment after receiving combination treatment for scars using fractional CO₂ laser and 595 nm PDL. Analysis of clinical indicators demonstrated statistically significant improvement 6 months after completion of therapy. The mean visual analog scale (VAS) redness decreased from 7.2 ± 1.1 to 1.9 ± 0.7 ($p < 0.001$). Scar height fell from 2.1 ± 0.4 mm to 1.15 ± 0.3 mm ($p < 0.001$), and scar tissue volume decreased by 45% (from 1.8 ± 0.5 cm³ to 0.99 ± 0.4 cm³; $p < 0.001$). A significant improvement in skin texture (by $38 \pm 7\%$, $p < 0.05$) suggests that the combined laser treatment is causing qualitative remodeling of the dermis.

Conclusion. The outcomes attest to the good efficacy and safety of combination therapy for scars utilizing fractional CO₂ laser and 595 nm PDL. Statistical study indicates a significant association between laser exposure parameters and clinical improvements, which allows proposing individual selection of parameters to enhance the therapeutic effect. The technique's clinical application is shown by its low frequency of adverse effects and high patient satisfaction

References:

1. Baranov A.P. Plastic surgery: a guide for doctors. - Moscow: Medicine, 2020. - 512 c.
2. Merzlikina N.S. Keloid and hypertrophic scars: clinic, diagnostics, treatment. - SPb.: SpetsLit, 2017. - 208 c.
3. Galitsky Y.I. Fundamentals of reconstructive and plastic surgery. - Moscow: GEOTAR-Media, 2022. - 480 c.
4. Tkachenko S.B. Modern approaches to the treatment of pathologic scars // Vestnik dermatologii i venerologii. - 2021. - №4. - C. 45-50.
5. Fedorov, A.V. Physiology of wound healing and scar formation // Surgery. - 2020. - №7. - C. 30-34.